

14 Metadata Syndication Things

Training Guide

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About

This resource is an output from two projects centred on data syndication methods developed by the World Data System International Technology Office (WDS-ITO) and funded by the Alliance (from NDRIO): one centred on traditional metadata harvesting and one centred on semantic markup.

The resource borrows—in tone and format—from the [23 RDM Things](#) training program developed at the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) and replicated worldwide. Our iteration, "14 Metadata Syndication Things," has a narrower focus. It introduces the subjects of federation and syndication through the lens of some key topics in harvestable metadata services and semantic markup (specifically schema.org), as technologies that enhance dataset and data repository interoperability. We present our 14 Things in five modules, based on the 4 FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability), plus a fifth section (Going Global) that takes a big-picture look at FAIR metadata within the context of a global set of research artefacts.

In this approach each module contains between 2 to 4 'things'. Each of the 'things' has an introduction, followed by a brief description of the 'thing', a set of questions to prompt discussion and a curated list of resources that delve deeper into that topic. Because one example can be worth a thousand technical descriptions, we illustrate the issues with current use cases and implementations whenever possible.

Audience

We expect this resource will be useful to data managers and repository managers (1) with intermediate-to-advanced technical knowledge, (2) in the earlier stages of their FAIR data and/or data sharing journeys and (3) who may be looking to enhance their repositories interoperability and/or explore the current data sharing landscape and current RDM approaches to metadata syndication.

Goal

With these 14 Things, we share part of the bounty from our recent expeditions into the metadata syndication ecosystem. This collection brings together research articles, blog posts, conference presentations, technical reference materials and other types of digital material selected for their relevance, clarity, timeliness and quality of content.

Findability Things

What is Metadata Syndication? According to the [ARDC](#), it is the process of sharing (or publishing—which may or may not be taken up by another platform) metadata records with other registries or search engines to increase their discoverability. Ready to know more? Let's dive deeper! The following topics address discoverability: two sections on metadata ([Thing 1: What is Metadata?](#) and [Thing 2: Semantics and Schema.org](#)) and another section on what its syndication entails ([Thing 3: Organizing for Discovery](#)). Research data managers must create well formed metadata that follows community accepted standards and formats, and expose that metadata in services designed to be consumed and enriched by both researchers and other value-added service providers.

[Data Federation: Standards, Best Practices, and Thoughts](#) is a recent [Research Data Alliance](#) (RDA) Workshop presentation (Crosas, 2019): a quick, summary introduction to data federation from the perspective of Dataverse—a hybrid platform that is both a repository and a metadata harvester.

Thing 1: What is Metadata?

“ Metadata, the information we create, store, and share to describe things, allows us to interact with these things to obtain the knowledge we need. The classic definition is literal, based on the etymology of the word itself—**metadata** is “**data about data.**” With this broad definition, one might expect that metadata could be found everywhere, and in fact it is. ”

Riley & Niso (2017): [Understanding Metadata](#)

Sharing your data products and associated descriptive metadata that includes information such as the creator, keywords, measured variables and licensing is an effective way to improve their findability. There have been initiatives to create a *universal* metadata standard in the past. However, pursuing a “one-size-fits-all” solution proved unrealistic, as adoption required broad consensus among heterogeneous stakeholder groups. Hence, over time, the RDM community has adopted a more effective strategy: developing extant metadata standards, and working to make them compatible with each other.

Table 1: Types of metadata and their uses (from [Riley & NISO, 2017](#))

Metadata Type	Example Properties	Primary Uses
Descriptive metadata	Title, Author, Subject, Genre, Publication date	Discovery, Display Interoperability
Technical metadata	File type, File size, Creation date/time, Compression scheme	Interoperability Digital object management Preservation
Preservation metadata	Checksum, Preservation event	Interoperability Digital object management Preservation
Rights metadata	Copyright status, License terms, holder	Interoperability Digital object management
Structural metadata	Sequence, Place in hierarchy	Navigation
Markup languages	Paragraph, Heading, List, Name, Date	Navigation Interoperability

Options for standards are numerous, detailed and cover information about the data itself, the machines/instruments used to collect the data (such as make, model and manufacturer) and any cleaning/analysis steps or scripts used to process or create data products. Hand in hand with metadata standards, controlled vocabularies supply standardized sets of property values, such that common metadata elements (fields) and their values (contents) uniformly describe the features using the same terms. Combining both strategies improves an individual’s or machine’s

ability to find the data they are searching for, while also providing the opportunity for communities of practice to actively share data. All of these factors are pertinent to curating robust metadata.

So what are some of the available standards, and what are some of their typical areas of application?

General Purpose:

- [DublinCore \(DC\)](#) Metadata Element is a generic set of 15 properties for describing a wide range of resources.
- [Metadata Object Description Schema \(MODS\)](#) is a standard used to describe a variety of types of resources; it is maintained by the Library of Congress.

Sciences:

- [Darwin Core \(DwC\)](#) is used in the biological sciences to describe collections of biological objects or data and includes a glossary of terms intended to facilitate the sharing of information about biological diversity.
- [Access to Biological Collection Data \(ABCD\)](#) is used in the biological sciences to describe specimens and scientific observations.
- [Astronomy Visualization Metadata Standard \(AVM\)](#) is used to describe data-derived astronomical images.
- [Ecological Metadata Language \(EML\)](#) is used to formalize and standardize concepts necessary when describing ecological data.
- [FDGC Federal Geographic Data Committee Standard](#) is a standard developed by the US Government for documenting digital geospatial data; it is especially relevant to researchers in the field of Geographic Information Systems.
- [ISO19115:2003](#) is used by the environmental sciences/geospatial communities. It is an internationally-adopted schema for describing geographic information and services.

Social and Behavioral Sciences:

- [Data Documentation Initiative \(DDI\)](#) is a standard for describing observational and survey data in the social, behavioral, economic and health sciences; it is also useful for structuring research data documentation.
- [OLAC](#) is a standard used by the Open Language Archives Community for describing language resources in linguistics research.

Arts and Humanities:

- [Text Encoding Initiative Guidelines \(TEI\)](#) is a standard for the representation of texts in digital form, and has been used by researchers in the humanities, social sciences and linguistics since 1994.
- [VRA Core](#) is a standard created by the [Visual Resources Association](#) for describing cultural objects, such as images and works of art.
- [PBCore](#), also known as the Public Broadcasting Metadata Dictionary, is a standard designed for the description of audiovisual resources in digital and analog formats.

Figure 1: Descriptive metadata standards include contextual information that is useful in understanding the resource. This figure depicts a sample of standards and the layers involved in the metadata universe. (Adapted from Riley, J., 2018, Seeing Standards: A Visualization of the Metadata Universe)

It is important to understand the benefits and constraints that each metadata standard entails. But the most important take-away is that there is no point in reinventing the wheel, it's always best to sit down, and have a chat with your domain community!

	<p>Consider: What kinds of metadata are your datasets currently implementing? Do they support the main descriptive metadata fields (e.g. Dublin Core)? What FAIR-compliant metadata recommendations exist in your domain community?</p>
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Resources:

- [ANDS Metadata Guide](#)
- [Defining Metadata: a DataONE Education Module](#)
- [Glossary of Metadata Standards](#)
- [Open Metadata for Research Data Discovery in Canada](#)
- [Understanding Metadata: What Is Metadata, and What Is It For?](#)

Thing 2: Semantics and Schema.org

The semantic web is a proposed development of the World Wide Web in which data or content in web pages is structured and tagged so that it can be read directly by computers. Markup in the semantic web defines not just links between content (like hyperlinks) but also the nature of the connections and the meaning of the linked content. As data managers and scientists have increasing volumes and variety of data to manage, discover and analyze, adopting semantic markup and related technologies is a crucial step towards automating workflows and leveraging the structures and advantages of the World Wide Web.

The goal of the semantic web is to make content machine-readable and actionable by making explicit connections between published content. There have been many markup languages developed in pursuit of this goal. Among data managers, the schema.org vocabulary mark-up is being utilized to enhance and automate the act of sharing metadata records with the world, and is a prerequisite to ensuring that your metadata records are included in [Google Dataset Search](#) (GDSS). The role of search engines will be elaborated in [Thing 3: Organizing for Discovery](#).

[Schema.org](https://schema.org) (SDO) is a controlled vocabulary used to mark up content in a webpage in a way that search engines can understand. The core SDO vocabulary is constantly under development, and it grows in response to use cases across many communities. SDO can be used to describe many different things (“object types”) referred to in a webpage, including recipes, job posts, book reviews and in our case, datasets and data catalogues. Generally speaking, the workflow is this: repositories have a database of metadata that describe their holdings. Data managers can use that set of metadata to generate a series of landing pages, one per dataset. That landing page is a web page generated from the database of metadata that describes the dataset and includes either a pointer to the data resource that can be found at the repository, or instructions on how to access the data. The landing pages are marked up with SDO terms. Bots then parse the web pages, index them and include them in GDSS. Importantly for those who manage sensitive or restricted data that are subject to privacy concerns, once a dataset is discovered in GDSS the user is directed back to the repository to obtain the data. Privacy concerns and restrictions will always be an integral part of data management and will be discussed in more detail in [Thing 7: Linked Open Data](#), [Thing 8: Data Licensing: As Open as Possible](#) and [Thing 9: Restricting Access: As Closed as Necessary](#)

Standard metadata formats like DCAT, ISO19115, FGDC, CSDGM and others define descriptive metadata properties such as title, subject, genre, author and creation date. In order to mark up the landing page with SDO terms, the data manager has to decide which metadata properties (the terms used in standard metadata formats) are equivalent to which SDO terms. Finding equivalent terms across standards is known as crosswalking (more about that under [Thing 4: Crosswalks!](#)).

Want to know more about SDO? Check out the resources below.

	Consider: Are you aware of any controlled vocabularies or semantic resources used by your repository?
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Resources:

- [Schema.org for Research Data Managers: A Primer](#)
- [Schema.org](#)
- [Schema.org Community Examples Github](#)
- [Schema.org External Resources](#)
- [RDA Research Metadata Schemas Schema.org Implementation Guidelines](#)
- [Metadata Harvesting through Schema.Org](#)

Thing 3: Organizing for Discovery

The following will outline some of the things that repositories need to know about searching for and finding datasets in federated systems: data catalogues, repositories' own search and access interfaces, and what kinds of added value web crawlers and other kinds of federated discovery can provide in terms of enhanced discoverability. Let's investigate how!

A data catalogue is a collection of metadata that describes available datasets, although many repository catalogues contain data products among a variety of object types. Its function is to describe and organize the resources available in the repository, so that users can find what they need. Typically, a local data catalogue includes an interface that supports faceted browsing and open text boxes that allow users to search fields in the metadata collected in the catalogue. Repository platforms can also provide more advanced discovery and visualization functions, by utilizing semantic tags such as schema.org mark-up in metadata, and by publishing and consuming linked open data, described further below.

Figure 2: An example of a federated data structure. Through the Joint Information Systems Committee (JISC) Research Data Discovery Service (RDDS), subject-specific data centres and university repositories in the UK can federate their content and make it accessible through international aggregators, search engines, and other data registries through the UK. ([Ball et al., 2015](#))

Federated discovery services can provide added functionality to repositories' local catalogue search interfaces, with the added bonus of making datasets from a local repository more visible to the community, as part of a larger (and usually better known) discovery platform. Without

federation, repositories are essentially relying on their own “popularity” to attract users to their catalogue.

Discovery services can take different approaches: some harvest repositories’ metadata catalogues, making copies of those records searchable on the discovery platform. This involves pulling updated records from repositories on a regular basis, and harmonizing (that is, crosswalking) them into common metadata standards. The end product is an indexed collection of metadata records aggregated from many single repositories. Some examples are Jisc’s Research Data Discovery Service (RDDS), and the Canadian Federated Research Data Repository (FRDR), shown in Figures 2 and 3.

Discovery services that use a harvesting approach, in which metadata catalogues are copied into one central platform, are working with federated content. Think of a harvester as a software application that pays scheduled, automated visits to repository catalogues, and grabs a copy of the most recent version of all metadata records or a filtered subset of them (also conveniently called a “set” in technical parlance). To provide access to the data itself, metadata records contain unique, persistent identifiers that point back to the original data source.

Figure 3: Metadata flows. Jisc’s RDDS harvests metadata from university repositories and subject data centres. The incoming metadata uses different standards (represented as arrows); crosswalks allow the records to be harmonized for interoperability with other discovery services. (Ball et al., 2015)

Figure 4: Canada’s metadata harvesting service FRDR provides a national discovery layer for Canadian research data. (Turp et al., 2020)

Canada has its own established federated metadata catalogue, *le Dépôt fédéré de données de recherche* (DFDR), a.k.a. the Federated Research Data Repository (though its friends call it FRDR, or *furr-durr*), represented in Figure 4. By federal mandate, FRDR is a bilingual service. FRDR pulls metadata from approximately [87 open data repositories](#) across Canada. It is a hybrid platform: part federated *metadata* repository, part conventional, run-of-the-mill *dataset* repository. This means that researchers and faculty members from Canadian post-secondary institutions, or their designates, may also use FRDR to publish their data. *Fun fact!* The way it’s

set up means that *FRDR has to actually harvest itself!* (Or rather, the harvester part harvests the repository part). This means that FRDR’s service development involves the additional challenge of ensuring that the underlying system can handle bilingual content ([Barsky et al., 2016, p. 19](#)).

In contrast to harvesting and aggregation services, some repositories will provide federated search services, where each central query is translated and transmitted between the search engine and remote data catalogues. Federated search is a technique for searching multiple collections simultaneously from a variety of distributed catalogues without harvesting their metadata. The Global Earth Observation System of System ([GEOSS](#)) platform is a good example of federated search across different services, namely, across “hundreds of heterogeneous and autonomous supply systems,” a.k.a. the “GEO metasystem.” At the heart of GEOSS, the GEO Discovery and Access Broker ([GEO DAB](#)) mediates the interaction between systems, translating queries into each node’s native query-language, and harmonizing the heterogeneous results into a uniform display format to be viewed back by the user behind the search.

Figure 5: GEOSS’ GEO-DAB’s visualization of a federated search and the process of mediating the interaction between its systems (image adapted from geodab.net).

Finally, another option for metadata discovery is through search engines. Search engines such as Google crawl the web and collect and index information across all sites. Like harvesters, search engines create an index with the data that is crawled but, unlike the former, search engines can work with poor-to-inexistent metadata, and algorithms have developed that are able to create an index using other contents, such as automatic keywords, or natural language processing (NLP) AIs to classify or make inferences about a document’s semantic contents.

Prototypically, the indexing done by metadata aggregators relies heavily on curated metadata records that use standardized vocabularies and schemas.

Pairing high-quality metadata enriched with semantic markup such as schema.org with advanced search-and-retrieval technologies allows search engines to leverage metadata's effective knowledge organization to provide better, more relevant search results. In that vein, Google created Google Dataset Search ([GDSS](#)) with the goal of doing for datasets what Google Scholar ([GS](#)) did for publications: providing a single interface to search and view simple metadata records describing datasets from thousands of data repositories around the world. Data repositories that have implemented schema.org on their metadata landing pages are eligible to be discovered through GDSS (examples of schema.org mark-up for a research data repository can be found at [science-on-schema.org](#)).

Our [Interoperability Things](#) ([Thing 4: Crosswalks!](#), [Thing 5: Persistent Identifiers](#) and [Thing 6: Machine Operable Interfaces](#)) delve deeper into the work it takes to make software and metadata work together.

Consider: Do you have a metadata catalogue? Is there any other organization that you federate data with (or wished you federated data with)? If so, what mechanism do you use?

Resources:

- [Discovery of Research Data](#)
- [Research Data Discovery and the Scholarly Ecosystem in Canada : A White Paper](#)
- [Taking Discoverability to the next Level: Datasets with DataCite DOIs Can Now Be Found through Google Dataset Search](#)
- [Understanding Data Search as a Socio-Technical Practice](#)
- [Data Discovery Paradigms: User Requirements and Recommendations for Data Repositories](#)
- [GEOSS Platform \(former GCI\)](#)
- [GEO DAB](#)
- [FRDR documentation - Describing your data](#)

Interoperability Things

The following Interoperability ‘things’ are a key component to putting the "ability" in findability! Interoperability is the capacity for computer systems or software to exchange and make use of information. As we learned above, the first step to metadata syndication is ensuring you have robust metadata, and determining where you would like to share it. The next step is ensuring that your robust metadata has the power to get to your desired destination(s). The following four Things: [Thing 4: Crosswalks!](#), [Thing 5: Persistent Identifiers](#), [Thing 6: Machine Operable Interfaces](#) and [Thing 7: Linked Open Data](#) lay out strategies for long-term computational compatibility.

[Research Data Repository Interoperability Primer](#): The main focus of the primer is machine operable interfaces, but it also contains a comprehensible collection of data and metadata formats and models focusing on the exchange of digital content in a generic way.

Thing 4: Crosswalks!

As mentioned in [Thing 2: Semantics and Schema.org](#), adding SDO mark-up can make your metadata discoverable in GDSS. Schema.org sounds great! But I have so much on my desk, how do I complete the implementation ASAP, you ask? With CROSSWALKS! Finding equivalent terms across standards is known as crosswalking. Crosswalks are utilized in all sorts of circumstances, including syndication.

In general, crosswalks are fantastic resources for their respective communities but require labour intensive work. So why spend time doing it? If a repository's metadata schema has already been widely adopted by a community, it is likely a crosswalk to schema.org properties has already been developed. Of course, it is easier to discover and adopt an existing crosswalk, rather than starting from scratch. The [RDA Research Metadata Schemas WG](#) has created crosswalks between metadata standards and schema.org properties. Crosswalks support data managers interested in SDO adoption, and promote consistent use of terms across research domains; the RDA RMS WG has collected 15 crosswalks currently used by data managers. The WDS-ITO has created user-friendly [visualizations](#) of the collected crosswalks to promote consistent community implementation and to facilitate the derivation of new crosswalks.

If there are no existing crosswalks for your metadata standard, it is still possible to utilize existing crosswalks as a reference point for similar properties that have been mapped in other communities and to point you in the right direction. The RDA Research Metadata Schemas WG [Recommendations](#) include ensuring that new crosswalks are openly available as early as possible. This is beneficial to both you and the community in order to receive feedback, which in turn will make the crosswalk more adaptable and adoptable. Additionally, if you are creating your own crosswalk(s), try to map as many properties to the terms in the destination schema as possible. If there are pertinent keywords missing, the user search may not be able to find the dataset, and the user may not refer to the originating repository for further exploration.

EOSC/EDMI			
EOSC/EDMI	description(M)	identifier(M)	name(M)
Schema.org Property	description	identifier	name
Schema.org Parent Type	schema:Thing	schema:Thing	schema:Thing

Figure 6: This snapshot is a visual representation of a crosswalk between three elements from the EOSC/EDMI metadata standard to Schema.org Properties and Parent Types. The schema.org properties

draw from different classes, hence why the parent class of the schema.org property is also provided (Welcome to Schema.org Crosswalks, 2020, <https://rd-alliance.github.io/Research-Metadata-Schemas-WG/>).

Consider: What tools/resources does your repository need to create a crosswalk?

Resources:

- [Crosswalks from schemas to schema.org](#)
- [How to Use RDA Crosswalks to recommend SDO Markup in Metadata](#)
- [Crosswalking near-Earth and space physics ontologies in SPASE and ESPAS](#)
- [Crosswalks: Transform your metadata](#)
- [TEI-to-Linked Data Conversion – DH2018](#)

Thing 5: Persistent Identifiers

Persistent identifiers are ongoing, long-lasting references to specific entities—publications, datasets, people and organizations. An identifier should have an unlimited lifetime, even if the existence of the identified entity ceases. This aspect of an identifier is called "persistence." When metadata is assigned a PID, users and machines are able to refer to and track said metadata record, as well as discover it through other registries.

We would like to further highlight that once an object has a PID, that PID can be tracked. This tracking allows resource managers to collect metrics about the use, distribution and impact of their resources. PIDs also make it easier to cite data and other resources. Citation analysis and citation metrics are important to the academic community and will be discussed further in [Thing 11: Data Citation](#) and [Thing 12: Measuring Success](#). For now, a well-known example of a PID system includes Digital Object Identifiers (DOI). These unique identifiers assist in providing exposure for published articles, datasets, software versions and a range of other research inputs and outputs. Also note that unique identifiers are being developed for [people](#) too! At least for the individuals who voluntarily opt to participate. The benefits of a PID system for people include assisting universities, funders and publishers worldwide in differentiating between people who may have the same name.

PIDs are imperative to metadata syndication because they are universal across domains, and widely accepted/recognized. PIDs are being used in all aspects of the data lifecycle, and aid in connecting the dots in data granularity, transparency and interoperability.

Consider: What system(s) do you have in place for ensuring the 'persistence' of your PIDs? Do you track your PIDs?

PID Systems and applications:

- [DOI](#)
- [ROR](#)
- [ORCID](#)
- [PID Information Types WG Final Deliverable](#)
- [Create and Manage DOIs for the Ocean Observatories Initiative \(OOI\) Data.](#)

Thing 6: Machine Operable Interfaces

Machine operable interfaces—Application Program Interfaces (APIs) and (meta)data exchange protocols—constitute the “software glue” ([CODATA](#)) that allows data providers to connect with data services and submit requests and queries and manage responses with each other. A data repository’s *interoperability*, its ability to interact and integrate seamlessly with other related systems and services, hinges on these middleware components.

If the distinction between APIs and protocols has ever struck you as blurry, it’s probably because they are often used interchangeably. One attempt to distinguish the two ([Jacobson, 2012](#)) defines APIs as “a way for two computer applications to *talk* to each other over a network (predominantly the Internet) using a *common language* that they both understand”—protocols being the conventional norms (the *style*), or the model that governs the interaction (*conversation*) between providers and services.

Figure 7: Schematic representation of metadata syndication (WDS-ITO, 2020). Content providers (repositories) send metadata to an aggregator using a standard protocol. The aggregator service connects to a search and discovery platform, where crosswalked metadata is indexed and displayed in a standard schema (Dublin Core).

A widely supported protocol for metadata harvesting is the Open Archives Initiative’s Protocol for Metadata Harvesting ([OAI-PMH 2.0](#)). For example, [OpenAIRE](#) harvests from metadata providers using OAI-PMH only, and the [Australian Research Data Commons](#) supports OAI-PMH

among various other alternatives. But it is also important to consider that while it is well established and also recommended widely—and it has the advantage of building upon two open standards, HTTP and XML—OAI-PMH is not the only metadata exchange protocol that might suit your repository’s purpose. To start, it is a fairly old (2002) standard whose original design was initiated by a group of libraries and archives motivated to create a federated catalogue of scholarly publications and other bibliographic resources. Alternatives to OAI-PMH include [ResourceSync](#), which was developed by OAI and NISO and endorsed in 2017 to expand OAI-PMH’s harvesting abilities beyond metadata, to include data contents as well. [DataCite](#), which maintains a catalogue of all datasets for which it has issued DOIs, allows other systems to harvest and query its metadata with the aid of multiple flavours of glue: a [web service](#) based on OAI-PMH, an API using the REST protocol, a [GraphicQL API](#) and an [MDS API](#). Other protocols that are common in metadata syndication systems include the Open Geospatial Consortium’s Catalogue Service for the Web ([OGC CSW](#)), and it’s the Open-source Project for a Network Data Access Protocol ([OPeNDAP](#)), or the Simple Application Messaging Protocol ([SAMP](#)), an International Virtual Observatory ([IVOA](#)) recommendation for astronomical data and metadata interoperability. As with IVOA, protocols that started out as data-exchange protocols were developed to incorporate specifications for metadata integration too.

Consider: What protocols do you find are most widely used among your repository’s “peers”? Are there any upcoming changes or trends in the data practices of your community?

Resources:

- [Research Data Repository Interoperability Primer](#).
- [Web Services Glossary](#)
- [Design and Implementation of a Custom OAI Search and Discovery Service](#)
- [APIs: A Strategy Guide](#)
- [Comparing the Performance of OAI-PMH with ResourceSync](#)
- [Increasing the Speed of Harvesting with On Demand Resource Dumps](#)
- [Open Archives Initiative - Protocol for Metadata Harvesting - Guidelines for Repository Implementers](#).

Thing 7: Linked Open Data

Earlier we described how including semantic markup in metadata enables it to be machine actionable and is a key component of the semantic web. In addition, we need to publish datasets that are structured in such a way that they can be linked to other datasets and resources, similar to how documents on the web can link to each other. Publishing data this way moves us towards the vision of the entire web as a distributed database, a Web of Data, instead of a collection of singular, siloed distributed datasets. This collection of interrelated datasets on the web is often referred to as Linked Data.

Linked Data is essential to connect the semantic web. A great example of this is the Europeana Linked Open Data Pilot ([2011](#)). The project created an approach that allows Europeana data providers to opt for their data to become Linked Data and convert their metadata to the Europeana Data Model ([EDM](#)), benefiting from Europeana efforts to link them to semantically related resources on the web. With the help of the W3C standards and Linked Data principles, data publishers link their data to other people's data to provide context. This is the prerequisite for getting the fifth star for Linked Open Data.

Linked Open Data follows a set of design principles for sharing machine-readable interlinked data on the web, and can be freely used and distributed. Linked Open Data is a powerful blend of Linked Data and Open Data: it is both linked and uses open sources. In 2010, Tim Berners-Lee suggested a [5-star deployment scheme](#) for Linked Open Data, starting at one star with data gaining more stars when proprietary formats are removed and links are added. The following are the 4 basic principles for linked data on the web:

1. Use URIs as names for things.
2. Use HTTP URIs so that people can look up those names.
3. When someone looks up a URI, provide useful information, using the standards (RDF*, SPARQL).
4. Include links to other URIs so that they can discover more things.

Figure 8: A portion of the Geography Linked Open Data Cloud from lod-cloud.net. This cloud is an interactive visualization that allows you to select any dataset and provides a description, star rating and accessible download links (<https://lod-cloud.net/clouds/geography-lod.svg>).

Linked Data extends common standard web technologies (commonly HTTP, RDF and URIs) to share information in a way that can be read automatically by computers. RDF has features that facilitate data merging even if the underlying schemas differ, and it specifically supports the evolution of schemas over time without requiring all the data consumers to be changed. RDF extends the linking structure of the web to use URIs to name the relationship between things as well as the two ends of the link (this is usually referred to as a “triple”) (Berners-Lee, T., 2006). Using this simple model, it allows structured and semi-structured data to be mixed, exposed and shared across different applications.

Consider: What is your repository’s star rating? Do you want to increase that rating? Do you currently publish LOD?

Resources:

- [The Linked Open Data Cloud](#)
- [What is Five-Star Linked Open Data?](#)
- [W3C RDF 1.1 Concepts and Abstract Syntax](#)
- [Vocabulary and Dataset](#)

- [Introduction to the Principles of Linked Open Data](#)
- [Linked Open Data -- Creating Knowledge Out of Interlinked Data](#)
- [The Europeana Linked Open Data Pilot](#)
- [Linking Data With Scholix](#)

Accessibility Things

So you have picked your metadata standards, ensured you are hosting robust records and implemented semantic linking and/or harvesting services to enhance discoverability. Now what happens if you are hosting sensitive data? The next 3 Things: [Thing 8: Data Licensing: As Open as Possible](#), [Thing 9: Restricting Access: As Closed as Necessary](#) and [Thing 10: Data Culture\(s\)](#), will detail how access can restrict/impact/benefit metadata syndication.

[The ANDS Guide. Publishing and Sharing Sensitive Data](#), outlines best practice for the publication and sharing of sensitive research data. This guide provides straightforward, step-by-step advice about what you need to know and do before publishing and sharing your sensitive data. Also see, ANDS [Ethics and Data sharing](#) for more.

Thing 8: Data Licensing: As Open as Possible

Licensing Data is a necessary staple in data lifecycle(s). In order to receive the full benefits from syndicating metadata, the RDM community has identified the need to have data remain as open as possible. As metadata is information about data, it is essential to include some sort of licensing information.

The European Research Council's [Horizon 2020](#) programme highlights that the key to innovation includes ensuring knowledge integration and data reuse. Their resulting Open Research Data ([ORD](#)) pilot places emphasis on the "need to balance openness and protection of scientific information, commercialisation and Intellectual Property Rights, privacy concerns, security as well as data management and preservation questions.'" Copyright refers to "the exclusive legal right to reproduce, publish, sell, or distribute the matter and form of something" ([Copyright Act R.S.C., 1985, c. C-42](#)). The following are common licenses that can be applied to data and are ranked by openness.

Table 2: Types of data licenses, ranked from least (1) to most (5) restrictive. The rankings were assessed by the ITO.

License Acronym	License Title	Ranking
CC-0	Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication	1
PDDL	Open Data Commons Public Domain Dedication and License	1
CC-BY	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	2
CDLA-Permissive-1.0	Community Data License Agreement – Permissive, Version 1.0	2
ODC-BY	Open Data Commons Attribution License	2
CC-BY-SA	Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International	3
CDLA-Sharing-1.0	Community Data License Agreement – Sharing, Version 1.0	3
ODC-ODbL	Open Data Commons Open Database License	4
CC-BY-NC	Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International	4
CC-BY-ND	Creative Commons Attribution-NoDerivatives 4.0 International	5
CC BY-NC-SA	Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International	5
CC BY-NC-ND	Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0 International	5

Of course, all license applications should be assessed on a case-by-case basis, ensuring that your data is as open as possible. The decision to restrict access to data should be consistent with the proper legal and ethical considerations of the data. With datasets, privacy concerns around any component of the dataset may cause you to restrict the entire dataset. Namely: (1) the dataset model or structure, (2) the data entry and output sheet, (3) field names and (4) the data or other content. Once a decision has been made, and the data owner has decided on the proper data license, the next step would be to ensure the license is captured in the metadata and is machine readable. As we saw above, some metadata records have a field for this information, and have semantic mark-up available, allowing for this information to be readily available to the end-user, either human or machine.

Consider: What licenses are currently applicable to your available datasets? Does it vary?

Resources:

- [Guide to Open Data Licensing](#)
- [Guidelines on Implementation of Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data](#)
- [Some Key Copyright Concepts for Librarians, Academics, Students and Researchers](#)
- [Copyright Act R.S.C., 1985, c. C-42](#)
- [Common license types for datasets](#)
- [Share Your Work](#)
- [The Landscape of Rights and Licensing Initiatives for Data Sharing](#)
- [Expanded Directory: Standards, Tools, and Community Initiatives](#)
- [FAQ for Research Data Licensing and Copyright](#)
- [Open Database License \(ODbL\)](#)

Thing 9: Restricting Access: As Closed as Necessary

Managers of repositories that contain restricted-access data—sensitive health data, Indigenous data, commercial data, embargoed data and licensed and proprietary data, among others ([Read et al., 2021](#))—may be hesitant to adopt interoperability standards or expose metadata for datasets or collections that cannot and/or should not be accessed publicly. Often, restricted-access research data ends up housed in appropriately safe, specialized repositories, an approach that “leads to fractured data storage infrastructure” and, in some cases, datasets that are too sensitive to host online at all ([Bar-Sinai et al., 2016](#)).

Data repositories have a responsibility to their stakeholders, which include data users as well as producers, funders, journal editors and other institutional partners or citizens ([Lin et al., 2020](#)). A user-orientation focus entails that these challenges must be addressed with regard to the data cultures represented in a repository’s target user group. With this in mind, the RDM community is tackling the access-restricted conundrum with a multi-pronged approach:

- Data sharing principles that address a range of ethical issues and data licenses that follow those principles;
- Safe storage for datasets, with trusted mechanisms to provide selective access to data with different levels of protection;
- Authentication mechanisms for eligible users.

Though restricted-access data is most frequently associated with commercial data or data from research with human subjects, additional ethical issues arise when sharing Indigenous data and metadata. This is because “all governments and all communities possess data that are inappropriate for widespread disclosure,” so Indigenous groups must “have the power to determine who has access to these data” ([Snipp, 2016](#)). In recent years, a few noteworthy initiatives have reframed data access principles to better safeguard Indigenous data sovereignty. For example, the [OCAP®](#) (Ownership, Control, Access and Possession framework¹) applies to the dissemination of Canadian First Nations information ([Farnel, S., 2018](#)). In the North, Arctic communities and researchers collaborate to ensure the ethical stewardship of Indigenous data and knowledge through the Exchange for Local Observation and Knowledge of the Arctic ([ELOKA](#)). Sovereignty over metadata is justified by the fact that it, too, can be “created and gathered, shared, manipulated and transformed, interrogated, and visualized” ([Farnel, 2018](#)) in ways that may harm Indigenous people.

¹ OCAP® “ensures that First Nations own their information and respects the fact that they are stewards of their information, much in the same way that they are stewards over their own lands. It also reflects First Nation commitments to use and share information in a way that maximizes the benefit to a community, while minimizing harm” ([FNIGC](#)). OCAP® is a registered trademark of the First Nations Information Governance Centre (FNIGC). Please visit the official site at www.fnigc.ca to read more about this framework in its original context.

Restricting access to sensitive data is justified, and repository platforms are finding ways to reconcile those necessary regulations with their commitment to open scholarship. One such way is [DataTags](#), currently being developed at Harvard's [Dataverse](#). The system is described as “simple iconic labels that represent a human-readable and machine-actionable data policy” ([DataTags Research](#)). Each DataTags implementation must define a set of tags based on its institutional data policies, which then would allow repository managers to establish a secure, streamlined workflow to implement access restrictions to data objects on a case-to-case basis. DataTags is currently being developed as a Dataverse add-on, with plans for a standalone tool and a software module for other repository systems to follow.

Meanwhile in Canada, researchers at Simon Fraser University (SFU) are working to implement “[zero-knowledge encryption](#)” in the Federated Research Data Repository (FRDR) using [Hashicorp Vault](#), to protect sensitive data from potential security breaches. Additionally, another Harvard project in development, the Infrastructure for Privacy Assured Computations ([ImPACT](#)), includes a [Trusted Remote Storage Agent](#) that acts as a secure interface to transfer metadata between the secure data storage server (where sensitive data is stored), and the Dataverse discovery layer.

Other systems are in development that allow data to remain in place in a repository, and allow that data to be “visited” by software or analytics packages delivered through virtual machines (VMs). This work is largely being piloted by health centres and requires an additional set of metadata on top of the data repository, creating what is known as a Fair Data Point. In this case the data custodian (often a hospital or centre for disease control) grants permission to VMs to query the data and run analyses at the data centre. This solution ensures that a patient's personal data remains in the local institution, accommodating laws and policies of the individual jurisdictions in which the data has been collected and managed ([Go-Fair, 2020](#)).

Finally, many repositories provide access to data products for users who are eligible through identity-management systems. Depending on the level of protection, single-sign-on with e-mail registration or OAuth verification may suffice to validate users, while more sensitive cases might require added levels of protection, such as having a human review new user registrations, and two-factor authentication.

Consider: What kinds of sensitive data is your repository hosting? Has your target-user community expressed any particular expectations with regard to access, data sharing ethics, privacy or related issues?

Resources:

- [What Is the Difference between 'FAIR Data' and 'Open Data' If There Is One?](#)
- [Sensitive Data](#)
- [Ethics and Data Sharing](#)
- [NDRIO White paper: Access-Limited Data](#)

- [Metadata as Data: Exploring Ethical Metadata Sharing and Access for Indigenous Resources Through OCAP Principles](#)
- [ImPACT use cases](#)

Thing 10: Data Culture(s)

It's often been said that technical solutions alone rarely suffice to solve cultural problems. Research data management is no exception: digital research infrastructures are “complex sociotechnical systems,” in which “social work is always interlaced with technical work, and vice versa” ([Poirier et al., 2019](#)). Much of the work of harmonizing metadata standards is carried out while trying to find common ground between stakeholders from diverse communities, with heterogeneous research practices, diverse ontological, epistemological and methodological commitments and sometimes competing interests. The following section uses two examples to illustrate how the global RDM community is mediating those differences today.

The [Research Data Alliance](#) (RDA) is an international community that builds the social and technical bridges to enable the open sharing and reuse of data. With more than 11k members from 145 countries, RDA strives to be an open space. Members can participate in focused global working and interest groups to develop and adopt practices and tools to support data-sharing and data-driven research. RDA aims to accelerate the growth of a cohesive data community that integrates contributors across domain, research, national, geographical and generational boundaries.

A different approach is represented in the [CARE](#) principles, formulated by the Global Indigenous Data Alliance ([GIDA](#)). CARE seeks to address the gaps found in the TRUST, FAIR and Indigenous data sovereignty initiatives (already mentioned in [Thing 8: Data Licensing: As Open as Possible](#) and [Thing 9: Restricting Access: As Closed as Necessary](#)). The CARE principles stand for:

- Collective Benefit**
- Authority to Control**
- Responsibility**
- Ethics**

The intent of CARE is to engage substantively with Indigenous Peoples' values and knowledge systems, and to protect their rights and interests through concrete, actionable measures that materialize the language in Diversity and Inclusion policy statements. Typically, the western mainstream conception of Open Data focuses on data sharing among entities on equal footing, while ignoring power differentials and historical contexts that may be perpetuating those imbalances. Initiatives like [OCAP®](#) (see [Thing 9: Restricting Access: As Closed as Necessary](#)) and CARE emphasize creating value from Indigenous data in ways that are grounded in Indigenous worldviews. They create opportunities for generative knowledge exchange, and they play a crucial role in advancing Indigenous innovation and self-determination. It is worth noting the intent of these principles complement the existing FAIR principles, encouraging open and other data movements to consider both people and purpose in their advocacy and pursuits ([Research Data Alliance, International Indigenous Data Sovereignty Interest Group, 2019](#)).

Consider: Which cultures are you a part of? Does your repository create inclusivity for its data owners? How can you and your team improve?

Resources:

- [Views of Ethical Best Practices in Sharing Individual-Level Data From Medical and Public Health Research: A Systematic Scoping Review](#)
- [Metadata, Digital Infrastructure, and the Data Ideologies of Cultural Anthropology](#)
- [Indigenous Data](#)
- [The Power of Data: Kahnawake](#)
- [Ownership, Control, Access and Possession \(OCAP™\): The Path to First Nations Information Governance](#)
- [CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance](#)
- [Data Sharing at Scale: A Heuristic for Affirming Data Cultures](#)
- [About RDA](#)
- [The Social Worlds of Research](#)

Reusability Things

In this context, reusability in the FAIR principles refers to the principle that metadata and data should be well-described so that they can be examined and/or combined in different settings. That is, a second researcher might use the same raw data to build the same analysis files and implement the same statistical analysis in an attempt to yield the same results. Reproducibility is a minimum necessary condition for a finding to be believable and informative (Bollen, K. et al., 2015). The following [Thing 11: Data Citation](#) and [Thing 12: Measuring Success](#) highlight common strategies in the RDM community for promoting the reusability of (meta)data.

[OpenCitations, an Infrastructure Organization for Open Scholarship](#): OpenCitations is an infrastructure organization for open scholarship dedicated to the publication of open citation data as Linked Open Data using Semantic Web technologies, thereby providing a disruptive alternative to traditional proprietary citation indexes.

Thing 11: Data Citation

Data Citation benefits all stages of data curation. For data curators, it provides proper attribution and credit, while documenting a bibliographic "trail," connecting publications and supporting data. For data users, it supports dynamic datasets and enhances discoverability. At the very least, citation benefits everyone by increasing transparency and reproducibility.

Article citation has been around for centuries, and has proven to be a valuable resource; the RDM community is trying to ensure that datasets receive the same amount of care and consistency. Specifically, the [Datacite guidelines](#) encourage research communities to develop citation systems that work well for them but recognize there are challenges with data publication that vary across disciplines. With this said, the following information is necessary in order to receive the benefits of a proper citation:

Creator (PublicationYear). Title. Publisher. Identifier

Citations generally embed a number of metadata elements, as you can see above. The data objects described by the citation are generally discoverable by this citation metadata. In addition, the data object is generally associated with richer metadata than is available in the citation alone. Furthermore, a persistent identifier is only a part of the citation process. Sound, reproducible research rests upon a foundation of robust, accessible data. The Task Group on Data Citation Standards and Practices has identified 8 "[first principles](#)" for data citation. The principles identify the benefits to all members in the data lifecycle and identify how the RDM community can not only adapt, but advance science through data citation and corresponding publication citations. The relatively new practice of linking the citation to datasets begins to address long-standing problems limiting our collective ability to locate data and reuse them effectively.

	<p>Consider: How will citations evolve with new and developing technologies?</p>
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Resources:

- [Out of Cite, Out of Mind: The Current State of Practice, Policy, and Technology for the Citation of Data](#)
- [Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles, Data Citation Synthesis Group](#)
- [Linking Data with Scholix](#)
- [Research Data Management Service Group](#)
- [IPSR Data Citation Guidelines](#)
- [Datacite Guidelines](#)
- [ESIP Citation Guidelines](#)
- [Scholix: A Framework for Scholarly Link eXchange](#)

Thing 12: Measuring Success

You're doing all these things to make your data findable, but how do you know it's working? A way to assess if your metadata syndication efforts have been effective is finding ways to measure your data's impact. Some ways of doing this are utilizing data citation metrics, search engine metrics and through certifications.

Citations are typically counted if found in reference lists of scholarly works that conform to particular formatting standards (which vary by data provider). Data citation is still rare in practice, with only half of journals providing instruction for how to cite data and more than 88% of all [Data Citation Index](#) records going uncited. Furthermore, 61% of articles in the social sciences fail to provide any type of citation to the dataset ([Robinson-Garcia, N. et al., 2015](#)). The Data Citation Index harvests citations to research data from papers indexed in the Web of Science. It relies on the information provided by each data repository, as data citation practices are notoriously inconsistent (or even nonexistent, in many cases). [DataCite](#) provides a tool to measure the impact of your data citations. They have created the [Citations Display](#), which takes all citation, reference and relation information between DOIs and makes it accessible in DataCite search. There are three components to the display: a citation counter, a citation chart and a list that separates the links by citations, references and relations.

Data managers can measure user engagement as an indicator of success using web analytics tools that track traffic coming to a site, such as Google Analytics ([GA](#)). GA provides information about your site and app users to better check the performance of your marketing, content and products. GA is an interactive tool that allows you to quickly perform ad hoc queries, easily configure and switch between techniques, sort and drill down into your site's data. Some of the interactive applications allow for adding and removing dimensions, and metrics use filters and segments to hone in on the data that's most relevant to you and your team.

Data citation is a metric of the uptake or engagement with a dataset, and web analytics can be an indicator of the success of your site, but at a larger, structural and organizational level data managers can look to certification by a trusted body as an indicator of success, such as the CoreTrustSeal ([CTS](#)) Trustworthy Data Repositories certification (formerly Core Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements). These requirements were developed by the Data Seal of Approval (DSA)–World Data Systems (WDS) Partnership Working Group on Repository Audit and Certification, a Working Group (WG) of the Research Data Alliance. The goal of the effort was to create a set of harmonized common requirements for certification of repositories at the core level, drawing from criteria already put in place by the DSA-WDS of the International Science Council. National and international funders are increasingly likely to mandate open data and data management policies that call for the long-term storage and accessibility of data to preserve the initial investment in collecting them, often as part of a data management plan.

By having the repository answer [16 questions](#) detailing the ins and outs of their processes, once reviewed and approved, the repository can claim to be a TRUSTworthy repository. These

questions ensure transparency for its users, and detailed information such as the technical infrastructure of the repository provides for data protection, as well as the repository's technical expertise in assessing data and metadata quality. Once a repository achieves CTS certification, it is then invited to participate with the WDS community. Although these two groups are separate, together they can provide a plethora of benefits, and help identify research data management best practices.

Consider: How are you currently measuring success? What certifications would help your repository? How could enhanced certification and metric tracking improve your traffic?

Resources:

- [Citation Analysis: Web of Science \(formerly ISI Citation Indexes\)](#)
- [Analyzing data citation practices using the Data Citation Index](#)
- [Metrics: Citation Analysis](#)
- [CoreTrust Seal](#)
- [CoreTrustSeal Application Management Tool \(AMT\)](#)
- [CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements 2020–2022](#)
- [Google Analytics](#)
- [Project Counter: The Friendly Guide to Release 5 for Providers](#)
- [Development of a Data Citations Database for an Interdisciplinary Data Center](#)

Going Global

Throughout this resource we have mentioned numerous times that it is beneficial for repository managers/members to consult and engage with other members within the RDM community. Benefits include, sharing resources, strategies, and lessons learned. The following [Thing 13: Global Networks](#), and [Thing 14: The World Data System](#) identify avenues to engage globally, and trends to look for in the future. Being aware of evolution in the RDM landscape supports the development of communities of practice in metadata syndication. Technology is evolving at an extraordinary rate, and having repositories engaging in meaningful discussions aids in these advancements.

[Arctic Data Ecosystem Map](#): The objective of this activity is to establish a map of the arctic data management “ecosystem” or “universe.” This is both a concept map indicating projects, services and relationships as well as a geographic map indicating location and this project utilized a linked open data endpoint that will allow people to query the database (i.e. using SPARQL). This is a great real-life example of how the utilization of technology and global coordination can enhance the RDM landscape.

Thing 13: Global Networks

Today's digital research infrastructures—in which data and metadata are shared along with other research artefacts—are built on the W3C's [Web Services Architecture](#) blueprint, a distributed computing model whose central feature is interoperability.

Thing 6 explained machine interfaces' key role in mediating between system elements and creating interoperability within distributed information infrastructures.

Figure 9: The EPOS service architecture serves as a model for the planned EOSC eInfrastructure (image by [Budroni et al., 2019](#)).

One key feature of digital research infrastructures, einfrastructures, open science commons and other types of research support environments is a federated organizational approach. In broad terms, according to a Knowledge Exchange report ([Goldstein, 2017](#)), “a federal approach is founded on the relationship between a coordinator level and distributed or devolved, autonomous hubs,” a relationship that foregrounds “ease of access to, or use of, distributed resources.” The same report defines research data infrastructure as “an ecosystem, a complex network of interconnected and interdependent systems.” The European Open Science Cloud ([EOSC](#)) is a key leader in this space, as are the Australian Research Data Commons ([ARDC](#)) and the International Virtual Observatory Alliance ([IVOA](#)).

Consider: What are the digital research infrastructures that your repository might consider integrating into? Are there any exciting new initiatives in your geographic region or subject community? How will the choices you make for your repository's technology and standards be constrained by the requirements of these initiatives?

Resources:

- [Web Services Glossary \(W3C\)](#)
- [Data Connections Strategy](#)
- [Connecting the Persistent Identifier Ecosystem: Building the Technical and Human Infrastructure for Open Research](#)
- [Data Communities: A New Model for Supporting STEM Data Sharing](#)
- [Architectures of Knowledge: The European Open Science Cloud](#)
- [The Evolving Landscape Of Federated Research Data Infrastructures](#)
- [Data Communities: A New Model for Supporting STEM Data Sharing](#)
- [Towards Interoperable Research Infrastructures for Environmental and Earth Sciences : A Reference Model Guided Approach for Common Challenges](#)

Thing 14: World Data System

The International Science Council ([ISC](#)) established the World Data System in response to the International Polar and Geophysical years (1882, 1932, 1957). It was largely born from the need to store the large amount of data created during those global science events and has grown to a consortium of data centres that incorporate emerging technologies and established best practices in support of multidisciplinary scientific activities. The WDS is governed by its Scientific Committee (the [WDS-SC](#)), which is appointed by the ISC's Executive Board. The WDS-SC is responsible for developing and prioritizing plans for WDS and guiding their implementation. The ISC-WDS represents a worldwide “community of excellence” with a mission to promote long-term stewardship of, and universal and equitable access to, quality-assured scientific data and data services, products and information across all disciplines.

WDS brings its [Member](#) Organizations together to coordinate their activities and, through that process, achieve an overall capability that transcends individual ones. Membership in WDS increases local and international scientific recognition by increasing exposure to potential users and collaborators internationally.

There are four types of World Data System members:

- (1) [Regular Members](#): Regular Members are organizations that are data stewards and/or data analysis services;
- (2) [Network Members](#): Network Members are umbrella bodies representing groups of data stewardship organizations and/or data analysis services, some of which may or may not be WDS Regular Members. They usually serve as coordinating agents for nodes that have common characteristics and mostly common disciplines;
- (3) [Partner Members](#): Partner Members are organizations that are not data stewards or data analysis services, but that contribute support or funding to WDS and/or WDS Members;
- (4) [Associate Members](#): Associate Members are organizations that are interested in the WDS endeavour and participate in our discussions, but that do not contribute direct funding or other material support.

Recently, the WDS has introduced a new [Candidate Member](#) category for organizations wishing to become a Regular Member, but that are not yet in a position to undergo [certification](#).

The science landscape is undergoing radical changes, with new expectations on researchers and data producers owing to policies from governments and funders to share data fully, openly and in a timely manner. In unison with the concept of Open Science, it is vital that the data underlying scientific research are properly preserved with openly shared access, particularly in relation to tackling the pressing challenges of sustainability and the resilient management of our planet. WDS facilitates scientific research by coordinating and supporting Trustworthy Data Services in the provision, use and preservation of datasets, in pursuit of a world where

excellence in science is effectively translated into policy making and socio-economic development.

Consider: How can taking part in a multidisciplinary community benefit your team?

Resources:

- [International Science Council: Action Plan 2019-2021](#)
- [WDS Strategic Plan 2019–2023](#)
- [World Data System](#)
- [World Data System Members](#)
- [WDS Working Groups](#)

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